

Review

Strengthening TVET System in Cameroon: Recommendations for Bridging the Gap Between Education and Industry

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Abstract: The quality of TVET graduates has been a significant concern for most industries in Cameroon. These industries complain about TVET graduates possessing low-level skills required for employment in the job market and a lack of confidence in carrying out their duties and responsibilities. Using a predetermined review protocol, this study conducted a systematic literature review to discuss extensively TVET institutions and industry partnerships as necessary for graduates' skills acquisition. It outlined the TVET concept and discussed the present status of TVET in Cameroon. The causes of a skill gap between the industries and TVET institutions were further explained. The paper also highlights how to bridge the gap between the industries and TVET institutions. Conclusions were drawn, and based on this review, the study offered relevant recommendations based on the success of some TVET systems in some countries to limit the gap between TVET institutions and the job market, amongst which are that TVET institutions should be tasked with oversight responsibilities by setting structures and policies that will facilitate industrial-institution links. In order to exchange information about the changing trends in industry practices and how these developments can be integrated into the curriculum, local industries and TVET colleges should collaborate to host seminars and workshops. This will greatly contribute to guaranteeing that TVET graduates acquire the right skills that make them employable in the labour market.

Keywords: Technical and Vocational Education and Training, Labour Market, bridging the skill gap,

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1. Introduction

It is worldwide recognised that the economic development of any nation is directly connected to quality education, especially Technical and Vocational Education and Training (TVET). TVET is a crucial tool for preparing individuals with the necessary skills to contribute to the development of a country. A developing country like Cameroon recognises the benefits of this system of education and has made efforts to promote it. TVET in Cameroon is designed to address the problem of unemployment and promote economic development by providing students with the necessary skills

(Godwill Mih Chewachong 2021). Therefore, TVET has the potential to decrease the level of unemployment among Cameroon's citizens. However, there is still a high unemployment rate among TVET graduates, and there is a persistent disconnection between graduates' skills and the job market's needs. This results from the challenges faced by the TVET system, which is one of the causes that slow down economic development. Like many developing countries, Cameroon is struggling to transform its system of education to be capable of producing skilful graduates while pondering strategies to enhance its economy (Che 2007). TVET is the key to facing these challenges and bridging the gap between education and employment by providing relevant knowledge to individuals.

In developing countries like Cameroon, TVET is an educational component that alleviates the level of poverty. Nevertheless, the gap between TVET and workforce skills remains a critical challenge caused by the weak collaboration between most TVET institutions and industrial partners. This has led to a situation where graduates do not meet the expectations of the job market and, hence, manage to secure jobs. Therefore, by emphasising the training quality of graduates, TVET can provide a competent and skilled workforce in fields such as agriculture, mining, manufacturing, etc., to help develop the economy (Wouleheu Moyou Ivan, 2023).

The Cameroon government took the initiative to set and implement the expansion policy of TVET education throughout the nation. The objective was to train skilful graduates for direct entry into the workforce that would contribute to the country's economic development. However, despite the increased number of TVET institutes, many graduates find themselves unable to fulfil the requirements of the job opportunities, and employers continue to complain about graduates' skills not being efficient for the available jobs (A. P. Tambi 2016). This circumstance has prompted scholars to raise concerns about the skills imparted to students to ensure the quality of TVET (W. Ngu and P. Teneng 2020), hence bridging the gap between skill and the labour markets.

Limited research has been conducted on how to strengthen the TVET system in Cameroon to limit the discord between graduates' skills and the job market. Therefore, carrying out further research on how to bridge the gap between TVET programs and the labour market needs will enhance graduates' employability (Sultan Idris et al. 2022). For instance, Ngu.W & P. Teneng (2020) focused on the influence of some TVET inputs on graduate employability in the Diamaré division, found in the far-north of Cameroon. The research emphasises the importance of the proper implementation of educational policy, infrastructures, curriculum and partnerships. The researchers demonstrated how TVET, such as the proper implementation of educational policy, infrastructures, curriculum and partnerships, can directly contribute to graduate employability in the Diamaré division. The study further emphasises how critical it is for TVET institutions to link their curriculum to the needs of the labour market and encourages investment in TVET education to enable these institutions to have the necessary and modern resources for the training of the students. Nonetheless, there is an insufficient analysis of the primordial causes of the skill gap between TVET graduates and the industry needs. Additionally, a thorough examination of other countries' TVET structures to share further details on empowering the TVET system in Cameroon was not explored.

Godwill Mih Chewachong (2021) thoroughly analysed the foundation policy of TVET education in Cameroon and the necessity of high-quality TVET to limit the skill gap. The researcher also highlights the contribution of qualified researchers to enhance the TVET system. He discussed the importance of upgrading TVET teacher training institutions in order to train qualified teachers with the required skills that will enable them to teach and transmit relevant knowledge to students. However, the study only focuses on the aspect of teachers being an obstacle to preparing students for the labour market. The study did not explore other issues like infrastructure, rapid technological advancement, outdated curriculum, etc., as causes of the limited connection between graduates' skills and the job market. Also, there is inadequate exploration of the TVET models of other countries to offer additional information on how to strengthen Cameroon's TVET system.

The existing technical skills gap between the graduates of TVET and the industry has become a significant concern for parents, business leaders, and educators in Cameroon. Employers of labour have continued to express their concern and worry over the quality of the current graduates of TVET programs due to their lack of relevant skills required for employment (W. Ngu and P. Teneng 2020). Most industries and labour employers in Cameroon complain stemming from the inadequate skill requirements of TVET graduates for most cutting-edge technology, low practical knowledge and lack of confidence in carrying out their responsibilities and duties. Most Cameroon TVET graduates must be subjected to several retraining programs since most graduates are considered non-employable based on the quality of training acquired from various institutions (World Bank 2018). Various studies have questioned the relevance of graduates and research results to the industry, considering the low academic status and skills acquired by the output of TVET institutions. The training program does not address the growing needs of the industry and society. A change of direction is required to close the widening gap between the TVET graduates and the industry regarding the requisite skills required for employment in the industries. In this light, a systematic review of the literature on how to strengthen TVET systems in Cameroon to bridge the gap between education and industry was conducted to provide evidence-based inputs. This research contributes to TVET quality improvement, limits the gap between graduates' skills and the job market and strengthens industrial cooperation in TVET systems.

1.1. The Concept of Technical and Vocational Education and Training

Cameroon, in its national policy on education, has given an important position to TVET because of its essential role in the country's technological and industrial development. It is recognised as an educational element that provides trainees with practical skills and basic technological knowledge. John (2015) defines TVET as a type of education designed to prepare the individual and learner to earn a living (to be self-reliant) or increase their earnings in an occupation where technical information and understanding of technology application, the laws of science and modern design production, distribution and services as essentials for positive change. According to Loveline (2021) TVET is that part of education where individuals acquire skills as well as basic scientific understanding. It is a structured sequence of classes and learning opportunities that starts with career exploration, supports fundamental life and academic abilities, and allows for attaining high academic standards, leadership, industry-defined work readiness, and advanced and continuing education.

Consequently, any educational endeavour promoting the development of technical skills and mindsets aligned with capabilities might be categorised as technical education. In the context of this study, TVET is a form of education set mainly to equip individuals with specialised competencies essential for thriving in the labour market or as a conduit for entrepreneurial ventures, thereby promoting economic productivity and self-sufficiency within society. The need to link training in TVET to either self or paid employment is based on all the best practices and approaches observed worldwide.

1.2. Aim of the review

This review aimed to systematically investigate how bridging the gap between TVET institutions and the labour market has been conducted during the 2007–2024 period in Cameroon. Specifically, the following questions were addressed:

1. What is the current status of TVET in Cameroon?
2. What are the causes of the skill gap between industry and TVET institutions?
3. What strategies can be used to bridge the skill gap between TVET institutions and industry?

2. Methodology and methods

A thorough examination of the literature was accomplished by finding and compiling primary research studies on the mismatch between TVET institutions and the labour market in Cameroon. I tried to use a methodical approach to synthesise the available evidence when completing this review to provide information to individuals involved in making

decisions, such as TVET members and educational leaders at all TVET system levels. Furthermore, by using this kind of study as an additional information analysis and mapping tool, one can get a broad picture of TVET practice across Cameroon and insights into specific field areas. When carried out meticulously, systematic reviews are considered a valuable and trustworthy tool for providing practitioners and policymakers in the TVET system with evidence.

Fig. 1: Literature search and selection of articles for review (adapted from PRISMA (2009))

From the initial search, I created four inclusion criteria to identify the pertinent studies: (1) published between 2007 and 2024; (2) all keywords or synonyms found using an electronic thesaurus contained in the abstracts: Skills Mismatch among Graduates, Technical and Vocational Education and Training, and the Labour Market.

As illustrated in Fig. 1 above, out of 51 abstracts from the published sources in the databases, 10 were disqualified for not having anything to do with bridging the gap between the abilities of TVET graduates and the labour market, and 21 were disqualified for not being relevant to Cameroon. A total of 20 abstracts were cross-screened using direct references to their full texts and satisfied all the requirements. Thirteen (13) publications were produced due to the process for an impartial in-depth review.

The reviewer evaluated the 20 publications based on how well they addressed the goals of the current review. I used a framework for evaluating the quality and relevance of evidence, loosely adhering to the "weight of evidence," to determine the degree of relevance in selecting which studies should be kept. As a result, 13 studies were included in the final evaluation after seven papers were eliminated for being irrelevant to the study's research goals.

3. Findings

I have come up with the following findings, which fall into four categories: (1) the current status of TVET in Cameroon, (2) the causes of the skill gap between industry and TVET institutions, (3) strategies to bridge the skill gap between TVET institutions and industry.

3.1. Present status of TVET in Cameroon

TVET's two primary goals are to prepare the workforce for self-employment and increase the productivity of the unorganised sector of the economy, according to the World Bank (2018). They made the point that the amount of training offered in public institutions has decreased due to a lack of funding. These reductions impede the pursuit of the primary goals of increasing production and offering training. Given the high cost of TVET as a form of education, the system must be extended and have sufficient facilities and equipment to ensure its success.

Similarly, Ngesi et al. (2024); Yaro and Shafak (2024) state that there is an insufficient connection between training and the workplace in both formal and non-formal TVET. They added that practical skills training does not yield the necessary skills for the labour market since it lacks a consistent mode. The trainees lacked the initiative, motivation, and training experience necessary to do their jobs well. Most developing nations, particularly Cameroon, have limited TVET in terms of scale, scope, quality, and relevance. As a result, TVET graduates face many difficulties in acquiring practical skills.

The curricula and syllabi are outdated, the programs are irrelevant to the local job market demands, and the institutions lack the supplies and equipment necessary for students to acquire practical skills. When it is present, most workshop and laboratory equipment is antiquated and has little in common with the technologies that are now used in industry (M. D. Tambi 2019). When practical classes are overcrowded due to inadequate training equipment, most students are unable to participate in hands-on practice and are forced to watch the demonstration. The lack of funding for these institutions causes the instruction and training to remain theoretical, and the job market does not view the graduates as having higher skill levels than their academic peers. As a result, the institution has a poor reputation and generates less employable graduates. A. P. Tambi (2016) claims that public TVET institutions have continued to face a lot of criticism. First, they did not know that ongoing education was necessary and could not train skilled personnel to fulfil industry requirements. Secondly, they are expensive yet less equipped for adequate training. The fact that these institutions' alumni frequently become unemployed is a sign that the training they received does not correspond with the available jobs.

In the majority of emerging nations, including Ghana, Nigeria, and Cameroon, to name a few. Both the formal and informal sectors' new skill requirements and the labour market's changing structure have proven too much for public TVET institutions to adjust their training. To support this claim, a recent poll found that over 40 million graduates remain unemployed in the workforce due to a lack of technical, vocational, and job-related abilities. In Cameroon, work opportunities do exist, but at the moment, there is either insufficient or no skilled labour to fill these positions it critically has to draw attention (Brenda Nachuah Lawyer 2019). According to Loveline (2021), young people and vulnerable unemployed graduates in Cameroon continue to see TVET as a lower quality of education.

The desire for an academic degree is growing among Cameroonian citizens, regardless of the campaigns launched or the volume of articles authored by experts on the benefits of Technical and Vocational Education and Training. It is popular in Cameroonian private colleges, but it was discovered several years later that most graduates are looking for professions that are unrelated to their academic background. Training is generally of poor quality, emphasising certification and theory above skill development and competency assessment.

A lack of teaching materials, outdated machinery and tools, and inadequate training for instructors contribute to the ineffectiveness of training and the inability to acquire the knowledge and skills necessary for successful employment. Appropriate workshop tools, machinery, equipment, sufficient training materials, and student practice are all necessary for high-quality skills training (John 2015). Clement (2010) states that insufficient funding, poor planning (including erroneous research data), inadequate facilities and infrastructure, teacher incompetence, inconsistent monitoring and evaluation, and subpar materials and resources are additional obstacles that prevent TVET graduates from acquiring

the necessary skills. Not only is there not enough money for education in Cameroon, but there is also a corrupt and misappropriated funding structure in place.

3.2. Causes of the skill gap between industry and the TVET institutions in Cameroon

The development of practical skills by TVET graduates has not been positively impacted by the teaching methods employed in TVET colleges. These teaching strategies include field trips, group discussions, the classic lecture approach founded on a solid theoretical foundation, and the Students Industrial Work Experience Scheme (SIWES). However, in order to address the issues facing the sector today, these approaches must be modified severely. With little to no contribution from local scientific research, the majority of multinational corporations in Cameroon obtain their primary and scientific research resources from their home nations. The primary institution's training facilities are antiquated and insufficient, making it challenging for practical training to keep up with contemporary industry trends.

Sewoyehbaa et al. (2023) claim that while training, funding, and curriculum development are hallmarks of industrialisation in industrialised countries, Cameroon's industries have little say in these areas. In terms of production and research, there is no direct connection or interaction between technological institutions and industries. Students' approaches to studying science, engineering, and technology principles and applications are impacted by the finding of a weak foundation in science disciplines.

Numerous investigations have also demonstrated the connection between workload and learning strategies (Godwill Mih Chewachong 2021). The constant animosity on campus has been linked to excessive idle time, which lowers the quality of training because the workload does not represent training in practical skills in detail. According to the schedule, the practical class session is devoted to pointless exercises. When fundamental concepts are not grasped, student learning becomes ineffective and results in low motivation. Below are the main causes of the disconnection between the TVET institutions and the labour market.

3.2.1. Rapid technological growth

TVET schools in Cameroon have the objective of training skilful graduates capable of satisfying labour market needs; however, technological advancement and globalisation pose challenges to these TVET institutions to fulfil their objectives, causing a supply mismatch (Chewachong 2021b). they find it difficult to adapt their curriculum to labour market standards, especially those with limited collaboration with private partners. In most TVET schools, private partners are not involved in designing and implementing the TVET curriculum. This simply implies that TVET programs rely on institutions with limited modern theoretical knowledge and practical inputs. This results in training programs that do not align with industry requirements. Consequently, there is an increase in the number of TVET graduates with limited technological skills in their field of study (Wignall et al. 2023).

Despite producing a large number of graduates, it is apparent that these graduates struggle to get employment in the labour market because they have insufficient technological skills. However, some TVET institutions have made minimal efforts to link their curriculum to the dynamic market needs. This includes updating their curriculum and providing their teachers with professional development programs to ensure the programs offered meet the demands of the current labour market and the training imparted to students aligns with the rapidly advancing technologies. Still, it has been noticed that the knowledge and skills acquired by most students are not relevant to current industry needs due to the limited involvement of private partners.

3.2.2. Outdated curriculum

The use of outdated curricula also appears to be a factor contributing to the skills gap between TVET graduates and the labour market. These TVET curricula most often do not consist of emerging technological aspects. The rapid technological advancement milieu requires graduates with current technological knowledge. However, many TVET institutions use outdated curricula and teaching methods.

Previous research reports that some educational institutions have not taken the required steps to ensure that the curriculum matches the labour market requirements and thus trains skilful graduates. Some researchers, Godwill Mih Chewachong (2021) and W. Ngu and P. Teneng (2020), opine that these learning institutions have trained their students based on outdated curricula, and according to Loveline (2021), this situation impacts the quality of graduates, as they are inadequately prepared to respond to the needs of employers, thus perpetuating the skill gap. This has also led to mistrust of the TVET system since the labour market does not value TVET graduates' qualifications, making it harder for graduates to obtain work.

Also, Sewoyehbaa et al. (2023) opine that the orientation provided by the current TVET system, based on students' competency, does not provide them with the necessary skills to keep pace with the demands of society and the labour market. The TVET education system does not emphasise bringing out the potential of students to provide high personal qualities and interests. This, therefore, limits trainees' potential, inventiveness, and chances to secure jobs. Therefore, to increase the link between TVET education and industry needs, as Suna et al. (2020) state, current technological aspects of the job market or industry and their future needs must be integrated into TVET programs to render them capable of preparing students based on labour market standards. Educational institutes can be deemed successful if they can match their curriculum to the demands of the labour market, thus producing skilful human capital (Husain et al., 2022; Teixeira et al., 2016). There must be a solid collaboration between TVET institutions and the industries to face the problem of "mismatch". These learning institutions are responsible for educating students and making sure that the curriculum meets the demands of the workplace (Ali et al., 2017; Bakar et al., 2014).

3.2.3. Teachers with limited qualifications to adequately train students

A noteworthy obstacle to strengthening TVET is related to the readiness of teachers. Most TVET educators lack the required competency to prepare trainees for the job market and do not have opportunities for professional development programs that could help enhance their skills. They are not exposed to industry trends, ensuring updates in their teaching methods. This results in teaching that does not match labour market standards. This implies that, even when the curriculum is well designed, it's been implemented by less qualified teachers. Only a well-designed curriculum can ensure the training of quality graduates. Therefore, Godwill Mih Chewachong (2021) suggests emphasising the qualification of TVET educators in implementing the curriculum, which is vital in training TVET students in order to reflect labour market needs and contribute to economic development. It is imperative that TVET institutions acknowledge the significance of updating teachers' skills so that graduates can acquire the appropriate training. The quality of the future human capital can be used to measure the credibility of educational institutions. Educational institutes that fail to hire or upgrade their educator's skills can be considered institutes with little credibility since they may have a hard time training qualified graduates. Therefore, TVET institutions need to emphasise continuous professional development programs and industry internships so that educators can gain adequate hands-on experience in their respective fields. This opportunity would enhance the teaching and learning process, thus adequately preparing the students for the labour market.

3.2.4. Insufficient infrastructures

Insufficient resources compromise the quality of education and training of TVET students. Most of the equipment used in the TVET institutions is often inadequate and, in some cases, obsolete. In Cameroon, TVET students are mostly taught based on theoretical aspects, making them no different from their general education counterparts (Sewoyehbaa, Nyounibe, and Bienvenue 2023). A good quality TVET system should be able to provide students with both theoretical and practical knowledge. Nevertheless, the TVET system lacks adequate material for the process of teaching and learning. This has made teaching and learning challenging, contributing to a disconnection between graduates' skills and the labour market standard since the students are not trained with the required resources, thus increasing the number of unemployed TVET graduates.

According to Husain et al. (2022), one way of supporting TVET institutions in acquiring the necessary infrastructure and training skilled graduates according to labour market requirements is by establishing a solid relationship between TVET institutions and enterprises. Nonetheless, some TVET institutions face the challenge of establishing collaborative models with industries to empower the TVET system in preparing graduates. Such partnership between the TVET institutions and potential industries helps support these learning institutions with the resources needed to prepare highly skilled, knowledgeable graduates with appropriate technological skills that can contribute to the labour market.

3.3. Bridging the skill gap between the TVET institutions and the industry

The industry's and technological institutions' ongoing skills gap has forced them to rely on importing trained individuals. What steps may be taken to close this gap? Many nations have faced this problem in closing the gap, and one way they have addressed it is by adding a significant technical component to their educational curricula (Brenda Nachuah Lawyer 2019). This typically takes many forms, the most common of which is providing students with courses in technology education, work attitude, and work principles. These are then followed by placements in commercial and industrial firms, where students gain practical experience in a genuine work setting. Several nations, including Australia, Canada, Germany, the United States, and Britain, have implemented successful schemes. The existence of a sizable industry sector that collaborates with educational institutions ensures the success of such initiatives in these nations. Some nations have decided to build training facilities with workshops that give students hands-on experience in the workplace. The private sector often creates, funds, and manages these training facilities, and schools pay fees for their students to use them.

Technical and vocational education and training skill development are typically offered as a stand-alone program or integrated into the subjects taught. The abilities are improved, including time management, critical thinking, self-learning, and lifetime learning. The best results have been observed when these processes are included in the curriculum of technological institutions as opposed to being taught as stand-alone courses. The curriculum ensures that students have the necessary information and abilities to use it in the workplace. Two crucial elements that have been determined to be required for both student groups—those pursuing training in technological institutions and those entering the workforce—are knowledge and skills.

In order to improve the knowledge of specialised students in TVET institutions, the government and the established private sector should also make arrangements for them to participate in the industrial work activities scheme, which allows students to complete short-term practical training in the careers of their choice. Our educational institutions, especially the TVET institutes, polytechnics, mono technics, universities, and other specialised training facilities, must develop and implement appropriate curricula. Therefore, to make the graduates of our technological institutions relevant to the demands of the industry, the curricula must be tailored to the specifics of our scenario and meet the needs of the industry primarily (Brenda Nachuah Lawyer 2019). Wouleheu Moyou et al. (2023) suggested that TVET institutions should redesign their programs to be responsive to the demands of the job market, especially the industry, in an effort to address these issues and create a relationship between the institutions and the industries. TVET programs must emphasise outcomes in terms of the knowledge, abilities, and attitudes that business demands to accomplish this goal. In other words, TVET should be provided in response to industrial requests as the countries below do to respond to the needs of the labour market.

3.3.1. China

The Chinese government has worked hard in the past years to expand TVET across the national territory and has taken initiatives to increase enrollment in TVET schools in both rural and urban areas (World Bank 2018). This has provided opportunities for young rural people to engage in the TVET system. The Chinese government has made a lot of investments in TVET; for instance, between 2006-2010, the government spent about 14 billion euros on TVET (World Bank 2018). In the meantime, many TVET changes were established in response to the dynamic society. TVET curricula are

regularly updated through collaboration with industry experts to ensure that trainees obtain relevant skills to meet industry standards (Li and Li 2019; Wang 2023). Both general fundamental skills and specialised TVET at the secondary and higher levels are integrated into the Chinese TVET curriculum (Gooptu, Bros, and Chowdhury 2023).

There is a strong link between TVET institutions and private partners which support the development and implementation of curriculum. These partnerships also support TVET institutions in benefiting from apprenticeship and internship activities provided by companies, ensuring students obtain hands-on experience according to labour market needs. Also, the private partners work with educators to assess students' performance to ensure that their skills meet the demands of the labour market.

TVET educators undergo continuous professional development supported by industry partners through workshops, international exchanges and training in contemporary teaching techniques. The Chinese government's initiatives to incentivise educators to gain skill qualifications, enabling them to work with the latest technologies and thus meet the demands of the labour market, is one of the aspects that sustains this TVET system. This initiative also improves students' engagement as they adopt student-centred pedagogy supported by ICT, which encourages them to participate and gain experiences (Gooptu, Bros, and Chowdhury 2023). The government and private stakeholders invest consistently to provide the necessary modern infrastructures for TVET institutions in order to improve the quality of training. They place a strong emphasis on training a skilled labour force to support manufacturing. This collaboration with top companies like Alibaba and Huawei has linked TVET programs to the demands of employers. The numerous decisions about TVET that have occurred in the past years reflect the Chinese government's goals to promote TVET according to current social and economic circumstances.

3.3.2. Germany and Austria

Germany has a dual TVET system comprising classroom and company instruction supported by industry partners. This system is recognised as one of the best TVET systems in the world due to its successful ability to train competent graduates. The system trains graduates with a national and universal certificate (European Centre for the Development of Vocational Training 2009). The regulatory framework for training TVET students in Germany is influenced by labour market needs (Haasler 2020). This implies that the TVET system is demand-oriented, focusing on training graduates that reflect labour market needs. The TVET system provides a wide range of programs and qualified professionals required by the labour market, and hence, it is considered a special tool to support labour market dynamism. By having a highly diversified field of training, it can be ensured that the system can provide skilled workers for almost any industry or trade (Zutavern and Seifried 2022).

The German TVET system has solid collaboration with private partners; this is one of the reasons the TVET system is globally recognised and successful. The curriculum is designed and implemented with both TVET educators and private partners to ensure programs align with industrial needs (OECD 2017; Pavlova 2019). The students are trained based on academic training and practical experience in various industries. This has led to the training of competent graduates and has contributed to reducing the unemployment rate among TVET graduates. Bosch (2023) highlight that the rate of unemployment of TVET graduates in Germany has significantly reduced compared to that of its neighbouring countries. This is a result of the dual TVET system that trains students with skills that are immediately applicable in the labour market, thus enabling them to secure jobs easily. Emmenegger & Seitzl (2020) emphasise that the labour market benefits from the dual system by the integration of a large number of qualified youths into the job market.

Other countries, such as Slovakia, have also started implementing the dual system with the active encouragement and support of the German government (Gooptu, Bros, and Chowdhury 2023). This directly impacts the skills acquired by graduates and hence increases their employability in the job market (ILO 2021). A country like Austria also implement the dual system, and this has changed people's perception of TVET. The government has made efforts to support the

TVET system and has emphasised its importance in enhancing economic growth. The dual system is comprised of 80% industrial learning and 20% classroom instruction. The TVET institutions cooperate strongly with industries. The industry partners co-develop and implement the curriculum according to labour market standards. They also support updating TVET teacher's skills and methods of transmitting knowledge to students. As a result, the graduates are competent enough to obtain positions in the labour market, contributing to the economic development of the country (Langthaler 2015).

3.3.3. Singapore

The TVET system in Singapore is considered one of the most effective TVET systems due to the high rate of employment among TVET graduates (Varaprasad 2022). The TVET system has undergone a lot of changes and rapid adaptation to industrial needs that have resulted in this solid current TVET system. This system can be used as an example for countries that have not been able to build an effective TVET system for the past year. It is built from the lessons learnt from some developed countries' TVET systems while applying these lessons according to its country's context (Varaprasad 2022). One of its unique strategies is its fast adaptation to the dynamic economy with the support of industrial partners. The government invest a lot in education, with about 20% of the annual budget, ensuring TVET institutions have the necessary equipment (Panth and Maclean 2020).

The industry contributes significantly to support the TVET system by providing industrial inputs in curriculum development and implementation to provide graduates with ready skills according to labour market demands. The TVET system also has future skills initiatives which involve preparing graduates with future skills. This initiative is managed by industrial partners, which implies the industry is the primary driver of this TVET system. The industry partners are part of the TVET advisory committee, providing ideas on how to prepare the students well. This system is well-defined and has been credible for the past few years. It is dynamic, undergoing constant changes from curriculum adaptation to the methods of teaching according to rapid technological advancements. The partnership existing between the educational institutes, industry partners and government to connect students' training to economic development is relatively solid (Varaprasad 2022). All these initiatives ensure that students are trained on demand-oriented skills, which has enabled TVET graduates to secure jobs seamlessly, thus decreasing the rate of unemployment and fostering economic growth.

4. Discussion and implications

Even if science and technology advancements are driving the rapid growth of Cameroon industry, there is an unprecedented need for graduates with advanced competency. The disconnection between TVET systems and the needs of the labour market stems from various causes. These include limited resources, outdated curricula, low teacher qualification, low public-private partnership involvement in TVET, and the limited link between graduates' skills and labour market requirements (W. Ngu and P. Teneng 2020). This has affected the economy by increasing the number of unemployed graduates among TVET students since their skills do not meet the requirements of employers. On the other hand, the industry frequently laments that the curriculum of the technological institutions that are now in place is insufficient to address the real-world issues facing the sector. This results from technological institutions' inadequate industry-appropriate curricula (A. P. Tambi 2016). Because of this, a gap exists between technological schools and the labour market; therefore, this gap needs to be closed to enable the employability of TVET graduates upon graduation.

The majority of Cameroonian enterprises have serious concerns about the calibre of TVET graduates, especially at higher educational levels. Low confidence, limited practical skills, and insufficient skill requirements for most cutting-edge technologies cause the majority of industries to complain. Since most Cameroonian TVET graduates are thought to be unemployed based on the calibre of education they received from their various institutions, they are subjected to several retraining programs. Every country's degree of human resource development, particularly in the fields of science and technology for industrialisation, determines how far it may advance economically. Despite the large number

of graduates from various technological institutions who have failed to positively impact the development of industries for the industrialisation of the economic sector, Cameroon is far from undergoing any landmark in technological development towards industrialisation due to poor infrastructures (W. Ngu and P. Teneng 2020)

The information base is growing more complicated, and the industry is expanding continuously. Commitment from all TVET stakeholders is crucial to bridging the gap between employers' industrial needs and the rapidly evolving technologies in technological programs. It is recommended that technological institutes provide an industry-oriented curriculum that is favourable to learning, as the business sector views these elements as addressing their demands. Curricula should be created to produce marketable, skilled individuals who can quickly transition into the workforce without requiring additional training. An essential component of reducing the gap existing between TVET and the labour market is improving and sustaining the cooperation between TVET institutions and industrial partners. Many successful TVET systems in the world have proven the impact of industrial partnerships in advancing their system. These partners can enable TVET institutions to align their curriculum with the needs of the labour market through the direct implementation of the curriculum by private partners. The private partners can also provide work-based learning opportunities such as internships and workshop programs (Ndlovu and Van Wyk 2023). This will solve the problem of outdated curriculum and provide hands-on experience that prepares graduates for immediate employment. This is observed in countries like China, Germany, Singapore, etc., how partnerships have helped to advance their TVET systems by integrating insights from experts in TVET.

Teachers also play a pivotal role in the training of students; therefore, they must be supported to enable them to have the required skills needed to train competent graduates (Chewachong 2021). This implies that continuous professional development is imperative to ensure that teachers remain knowledgeable, deliver relevant knowledge to students that will make them ready for the job market, and remain updated about technological advancement. Industrial partners can also support teachers by providing practical training that is crucial for TVET (Godwill Mih Chewachong 2021). Every initiative should be supported by reforms and comprehensive policies that promote the connection between the TVET system and the labour market. Therefore, policies related to the provision of resources, curriculum updates, partnership involvement, and incentivising partners to encourage them to contribute to the training of students should be established. To ensure the success of these policies, regular monitoring and assessment should be done by a committed and competent committee. By so doing, Cameroon can strengthen its TVET system, ensuring it responds to the needs of the job market and thus increasing economic development.

Recommendations for other reviews

I highly recommend that future assessments broaden their search outside English language and education databases, considering the constraints imposed by the resources available for this review. Grey literature, such as unpublished thesis and NGO reports on TVET activities, should also be included. By doing this, the review would be able to include more insightful opinions and viewpoints, especially from obscure places regarding TVET evidence. In general, Technical and Vocational Education (TVET) assessments ought to be promoted and carried out collaboratively by academics from different nations, aiming to improve the calibre of data regarding the idea of empowering the TVET system.

Conclusion

The review highlighted several significant facets of the gap between TVET and the labour market. Because it influences production and the advancement of social and economic spheres. TVET is regarded as the cornerstone of industrialisation in industrialised nations worldwide. However, most training programs offered by TVET institutions in developing nations like Cameroon are out of step with the labour markets and industry's demands and goals. The institutes lack proper infrastructure and workshop facilities and inadequate funding. There is practically little connection between TVET graduates and the industry. Nonetheless, students, instructors, and the industry will all greatly benefit from the creation of programs linking TVET institutes and the industry. This will give the companies a chance to assess the highly

motivated TVET graduates' performance, ultimately serving as a foundation for the industries to look for future full-time personnel. Therefore, to create a successful collaboration between the industries and TVET institutions, local industries and TVET institutions should plan training and workshop sessions to exchange knowledge about evolving trends in industrial practices and how these changes can be integrated into the curriculum. This will strengthen TVET institutions and help to bridge the gap between graduates' skills and the labour market.

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